

Er³⁺ doped amorphous tellurite thin films

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Abstract

Radio Frequency (RF) magnetron sputtering was used to deposit amorphous tellurite thin films from glassy targets from TeO₂-ZnO-Na₂O/BaO/Bi₂O₃ system doped with 2.5 mol% of Er₂O₃. The impact of the sputtering power on the optical, luminescence and structural properties of the films is discussed. The deposition process leads to amorphous and transparent films which emit light in the visible and NIR confirming the presence of Er³⁺ in the films' network. Owing

to their large refractive index and stability overtime, the Bi containing films are potential materials for integrated photonics and optical switches.

Keywords: glass, tellurium/tellurium compounds, erbium/erbium compounds, magnetron sputtering, thin films.

Introduction

Rare-earth (RE) doped materials are of great interest as they are a solution for lasers and optical amplifiers, widely used in integrated photonics and optical telecommunications. When doped with erbium ions (Er^{3+}), these materials can emit light in the visible, Near Infrared (NIR) and Mid Infrared (MIR).¹ Glasses are good hosts for RE, especially the tellurite glasses since they possess interesting properties such as low phonon energy ($\sim 700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), a transmission window from ~ 0.4 to $\sim 5 \mu\text{m}$ and high linear refractive index (from ~ 1.8 to ~ 2.3 at 532 nm).²⁻⁵ Compared to silica glass, they usually have a broad emission band and high emission cross-section.⁶ Furthermore, they can incorporate large amount of RE without forming clusters which is important when developing Er^{3+} doped amplifiers for integrated photonics.⁷

Recently, Lemiere et al.⁸ reported a study on the impact of tellurite glass composition on the Er^{3+} spectroscopic properties and demonstrated that Er^{3+} doped tellurite glasses in the TeO_2 – ZnO – Na_2O ($\text{BaO}/\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3$) system exhibit promising Er^{3+} spectroscopic properties. These glasses were prepared with a high concentration of Er^{3+} (2.5 mol% of Er_2O_3) and the variation in the glass composition was found to change the glass structure impacting the Er^{3+} spectroscopic properties. The tellurite glass containing Bi_2O_3 was reported with the highest intensity of upconversion and emission in NIR and MIR under 980 nm pumping and lowest hydroxyl group ($-\text{OH}$) content owing to its least polymerized network.⁹ Consequently, this glass is expected to be promising for integrated photonics.

For integrated photonics, the glass needs to be deposited as a thin film onto a substrate.¹⁰ Various techniques based on physical and chemical methods have been developed to deposit glasses as films.¹¹⁻¹⁴ Within the scope of physical deposition methods, Pulsed Laser Deposition (PLD) technique has been successfully used for the deposition of thin films with good quality and in various glassy systems.^{15, 16} For example, amorphous tellurite films were deposited using argon fluoride (ArF) excimer laser (193 nm) from glasses in the $\text{TeO}_2\text{-P}_2\text{O}_5\text{-Na}_2\text{O-ZnF}_2$ ¹⁷ and $\text{TeO}_2\text{-ZnO-ZnF}_2$ ¹⁸ systems. Radio-frequency (RF) magnetron sputtering is another approach to fabricate thin films. Compared to evaporation based deposition techniques, RF magnetron sputtering can be performed at lower temperatures with less deterioration to the target material since it is momentum based while resulting in better adhesion of the film onto the substrate.^{19,}²⁰ It is clear that both techniques are suitable to deposit thin films from glass. PLD does offer advantages over RF magnetron sputtering when it comes to depositing polymeric materials.^{21,}²² Interestingly, in the study performed by Schröder et al. both PLD and RF magnetron sputtering have been used in conjunction to deposit smoother and denser TiO_2 and $\text{Bi}_2\text{FeCrO}_6$ films.²³ Nevertheless, the good reproducibility of deposited films while having uniformity in thickness is inarguably a well-known benefit of the sputtering process while also aiding to keep the substrate at a stable desired temperature during deposition.^{24, 25} Subsequently, RF sputtering has been widely used to deposit films for various applications related to integrated circuits, sensing, solar cells, etc.^{26, 27} Demonstration of film deposition from glass within more complex system such as the $\text{MgO-CaO-P}_2\text{O}_5\text{-SiO}_2$ system was reported.²⁸ Surprisingly, very few studies on the deposition of tellurite glasses with compositions such as $\text{TeO}_2\text{-ZnO-Bi}_2\text{O}_3$ and $\text{TeO}_2\text{-WO}_3\text{-Bi}_2\text{O}_3$ using RF magnetron sputtering have been reported.²⁹⁻³¹ This paper presents a study focused on the deposition of amorphous thin tellurite films using RF magnetron sputtering. The chemical composition as well as the structural, optical and

spectroscopic properties of the films are assessed and discussed as a function of the glass composition and deposition parameters used.

Methods

Melt quenching technique was used to prepare tellurite glasses with the composition 68.25 TeO₂ – 19.5 ZnO – 9.75 X – 2.5 Er₂O₃ (mol%) with X = BaO, Bi₂O₃, Na₂O.⁸ The glasses are hereby referred to as TeBa, TeBi and TeNa, respectively. Commercially available raw materials were used: TeO₂ (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.99%), ZnO (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.99%), BaO (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.99%), Na₂CO₃ (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.5%), Bi₂O₃ (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.99%), and Er₂O₃ (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.99%). The 65 g glass batches were placed in a platinum crucible and melted at 775 °C for 40 min. After melting, the glasses were quenched in a cylindrical 2” mold to obtain glass targets with the desired shape required for sputtering. After quenching, the glasses were annealed for 6 h at 40 °C below their respective glass transition temperature. Finally, the annealed glass disks with a 2” diameter were surface grinded to achieve a thickness within 3 to 3.5 mm and flat parallel surfaces using a bench-top polisher (PM5 Precision Lapping & Polishing system, Logitech).

The films deposition was carried out using RF magnetron sputtering (MPE600, Plassys–Bestek) using argon plasma at Room Temperature (RT). The argon-oxygen (Ar:O₂) gas flow ratio was fixed at 40:10 sccm for all depositions following a study performed on the tellurite-bismuth glass system.²⁹ Sputtering power was varied in 10 W increment from 30 to 50 W for TeBa depositions. TeBi and TeNa depositions were performed at lower power levels, 20 and 30 W to ensure no damage to the sputtering targets. The substrates were rotated at 5 rpm and the chamber was maintained at an overall pressure of 0.5 mbar. Substrates used for the depositions were BK7 glass (Schott), <100> single crystalline p-type silicon (Si) wafers and

oxidized silicon (SiO₂/Si) wafers. After deposition, the films were stored in nitrogen atmosphere.

The X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) patterns of the films were measured using an X-Ray diffractometer (PANalytical Empyrean) under a Cu K_α line with 99 s step time, 0.026° step size.

The elemental composition of the films was analyzed using a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) LYRA 3 (Tescan) equipped with Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDX) analyzer AZtec X-Max 20 (Oxford Instruments) coupled with AZtec software (Oxford Instruments). The bulk and film samples were coated with carbon (Leica ACE200) to minimize the charging.

Variable Angle Spectroscopic Ellipsometry (VASE) was used to determine the thickness, the refractive index (RI) and the optical bandgap. The measurements were performed with a rotating analyzer ellipsometer (VASE, J.A. Woollam) at an angle of incidence from 50° to 70° in 10° increments over the wavelength range 280–2300 nm. The Cody-Lorentz model³² and Cauchy model³³ were used to fit the VASE data of thin films and targets, respectively. The RI dispersion of the thin films and the targets were also measured in the 2300–20000 nm range using a second ellipsometer (IR-VASE, J.A. Woollam) with a 16 cm⁻¹ resolution. The Gaussian oscillator model^{34,35} was used for data fitting using WVASE software. Modelling required the use of two gaussians. The Phonon Absorption (PA) edge of the glasses was determined from the absorption spectrum of the glasses³⁶ and was found to be at ~855 cm⁻¹ for the TeBa target and films, at ~810 cm⁻¹ and at ~865 cm⁻¹ for the TeBi target and films respectively, and for the TeNa target and films at ~836 cm⁻¹ and ~865 cm⁻¹ respectively. These PA edge values are similar to those reported for tellurite glasses.³⁶ The accuracy for the RI determination is ± 0.01.

The transmittance spectra of the films were measured using an UV-VIS-NIR spectrophotometer (LAMBDA 1050+, Perkin Elmer) at step size of 1 nm over the wavelength

range 180–2500 nm. The optical bandgap (E_g) of the sputtered films was estimated by generating a Tauc plot.^{37,38}

Surface topography and roughness of the film were measured using Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) (NTEGRA ACADEMIA, NT-MDT) with a single-crystal silicon tip (HA_NC, ScanSens GmbH) having a force constant and resonant frequency of 12 N/m and 235 kHz respectively under semi-contact mode. Scan resolution of 512 lines was chosen for an area of 5×5 sq. μm . Macroscale surface was mapped using an optical profiler (Wyko NT1100, Veeco Instruments) at $1.2\times$ magnification ($2.5\times$ for objective lens and $0.5\times$ for field of view lens). The entire surface was mapped using the stitch option. The surface roughness in terms of Root Mean Square (RMS), was measured for all the investigated films immediately after deposition and 8 months after deposition.

The emission spectra of the bulk glasses and deposited films were measured in the visible range using a micro-Raman system (alpha300R, Witec; Oxford Instruments) using a silicon drift detector. The excitation source was a 532 nm continuous wave diode laser with the measurement performed at 17.5 mW power and 1s integration time. The NIR emission spectra of the films were collected using an excitation at 808 nm from a pulsed laser with a 5 MHz repetition rate. Measurements were performed using a 300-line grating, 1 μm blazed. A lock-in amplifier and a liquid nitrogen cooled indium arsenide antimonide detector were used.

The Raman spectra of the films were measured using a 405 nm excitation source (alpha300R, Witec; Oxford Instruments) and the experimental setup consisted of a 600-line grating, $100\times$ microscope objective and were averaged on a 20×20 sq. μm zone.

Results and Analysis

Er³⁺ doped tellurite thin films within the TeO₂-ZnO-Na₂O/BaO/Bi₂O₃ system were deposited using different RF magnetron sputtering power as summarized in **Table 1**. For a comparable sputtering power (30 W), the largest deposition rate was observed for the TeBi thin films.

Table 1: Thickness of deposited films determined from VASE for different sputtering power values along with deposition rate.

Sputtering power (W)	Film thickness (nm) ± 5 nm	Deposition rate (nm/min) ± 0.1 nm/min
TeBa		
30	800	4.4
40	885	6.6
50	700	9.3
TeBi		
20	940	3.9
30	1205	8.1
TeNa		
20	975	4.1
30	745	7.1

The XRD patterns of all the films shown in **Figure 1** did not depict any peaks, suggesting that no significant crystallization had occurred during the film deposition for all glass compositions.

The crystals might have also been too small and/or too few to be detected.

Figure 1: XRD pattern of investigated thin films.

The composition of the films was verified using SEM coupled with EDX (**Table 2**). The deposition process led to an increase in the amount of barium (Ba) and bismuth (Bi) at the expense of tellurium (Te). However, the sputtering power had no significant impact on the film composition (within the accuracy of the measurement). The at% of erbium (Er) in all the investigated films was as targeted within the accuracy of the measurement (± 1 at%).

Table 2: Chemical composition of the investigated films compared to that of the bulk target glasses.

Element	Composition (at%) (± 1 at%)														
	TeBa					TeBi					TeNa				
	Te	Zn	Ba	Er	O	Te	Zn	Bi	Er	O	Te	Zn	Na	Er	O
Theoretical	25	7	4	2	63	22	6	6	2	63	24	7	7	2	61
Bulk target	25	8	3	2	62	22	7	6	2	63	24	6	9	2	59
Film – 20 W						17	7	8	1	67	20	6	9	1	63
Film – 30 W	15	10	6	3	67	15	7	10	1	67	21	6	9	2	62
Film – 40 W	17	9	5	2	66										
Film – 50 W	18	9	6	2	65										

The structure of the films was investigated using Raman spectroscopy. The Raman spectra of the films, normalized to the band at 780 cm^{-1} , are depicted in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2: Normalized Raman spectra of the TeBa (a), TeBi (b) and TeNa (c) films deposited using different sputtering powers on silicon substrate.

The Raman spectra showed various bands which are similar to those reported for the bulk glasses.⁸ As compared to the Raman spectra of the bulk glasses, a band (1) with large intensity

could be seen at $\sim 520.7 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which could be related to the signal from the Si substrate but it overlapped with the well-known band in the $400\text{--}500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ range assigned to symmetrical bending of Te–O–Te/O–Te–O bonds³⁹ and to Zn–O–Zn/Zn–O–Te bridges.⁴⁰ The band at 660 cm^{-1} ((2) in **Figure 2a**) was assigned to the asymmetric Te–O stretching and symmetric stretching of TeO_4 units. The band at 770 cm^{-1} ((3) in **Figure 2a**) was assigned to the symmetric stretching in TeO_3 and TeO_{3+1} units.^{41, 42} Finally, the band at $\sim 980 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (420.7 nm) ((4) in **Figure 2a**) was assigned to the ${}^4\text{F}_{3/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{I}_{15/2}$ emission from Er^{3+} . An increase in the sputtering power led to a slight decrease in intensity of the band at 660 cm^{-1} compared to that of 770 cm^{-1} suggesting an increase in number of TeO_3 and TeO_{3+1} units at the expense of TeO_4 units. The TeBi films are suspected to have the most depolymerized network as evidenced by the lowest intensity of the band at 660 cm^{-1} compared to the band at 770 cm^{-1} .

Irrespective of the deposition power, highly transparent thin films were obtained as verified from their transmittance spectra (**Figure 3**).

Figure 3: Transmittance spectra of the TeBa (a), TeBi (b) and TeNa (c) films deposited using different sputtering powers on BK7 substrate.

Over the entire scan range of the UV-VIS-NIR spectrum, the interference maxima reached 92%, equal to that of the BK7 substrate. The interference fringes were well pronounced and displayed a good optical quality of the films.

TeO₂ being a conditional glass former requires the presence of modifiers such as ZnO to alter the trigonal bipyramidal TeO₄ units to TeO₃₊₁ or trigonal pyramidal TeO₃ units. The incorporation of BaO, Bi₂O₃ and Na₂O into the glass matrix further influences the depolymerization which in turn leads to different ratios of TeO₃:TeO₃₊₁ units. In their study, Santos et al. observed that an increase in concentration of different modifiers into the TeO₂ glass resulted in a lowering of bandgap values.⁴³ This change in bandgap was expected since moving from crystalline to amorphous state, the k-space was bound to change, thereby modifying the electron density and position of valence and conduction band. As a result, the optical bandgap was influenced by factors, with one such as the Non-Bridging Oxygens.⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶ Owing to these, it was possible for the material to display a bandgap that was either purely direct or indirect or display both simultaneously. Furthermore, even for the bulk and film form of amorphous TeO₂, the optical bandgap was found to vary between direct and indirect.^{47, 48} In this study, all the investigated films displayed purely an indirect optical bandgap as shown in

Figure 4, depicted by a Tauc plot for indirect allowed transition ($n = 2$ in $(\alpha h\nu)^{\frac{1}{n}}$).

Figure 4: Tauc plots for an indirect allowed transition shown for TeBa, TeBi and TeNa films (a, b and c) deposited using various sputtering power, respectively.

Table 3 lists the optical bandgap which was obtained by extrapolating the linear fit of the linear portion to the intercept on the X-axis. The sputtering power had no significant impact on the position of the bandgap. TeBi and TeNa films displayed similar bandgap values whereas the

TeBa films had the highest band gap. Indeed, a bandgap located at the highest wavelengths was also reported for the TeBi glass bulk in.⁸

Table 3: Optical bandgap of deposited films determined from Tauc plot and from VASE with Mean Squared Error (MSE) fit values for different sputtering power values.

Sputtering power (W)	Optical bandgap from Tauc plot (eV)	Optical bandgap from VASE (eV)
TeBa films		
30	3.37 ± 0.01	3.68 ± 0.06
40	3.37 ± 0.01	3.65 ± 0.11
50	3.42 ± 0.01	3.65 ± 0.11
TeBi films		
20	3.29 ± 0.01	3.43 ± 0.01
30	3.27 ± 0.01	3.37 ± 0.02
TeNa films		
20	3.25 ± 0.01	3.40 ± 0.07
30	3.24 ± 0.01	3.51 ± 0.09

Also listed in **Table 3** is the optical bandgap of the films estimated from VASE, confirming that TeBa films had larger bandgap than the TeBi and TeNa films. However, these bandgaps tended to be higher than the ones obtained from the Tauc plots.

Due to the lower amount of Te in the films in comparison with the targets, the films had a lower RI than the corresponding targets as shown in **Figure 5**. From all the investigated films, the TeBi films had the highest RI due to the high polarizability of Bi.⁴⁹

Figure 5: RI dispersion curves from 300 nm to 20 μm for TeBa (a), TeBi (b) and TeNa (c) films deposited using different sputtering powers on BK7 glass substrate.

The presence of Er^{3+} in the films was confirmed by recording the emission spectra of the films using excitation at 532 nm (**Figure 6**) and at 808 nm (**Figure 7**). The emission spectra under 532 nm excitation, shown in **Figure 6**, were normalized to the band at 660 nm. They depicted two emission bands centered at 550 and 660 nm which could be related to the $^4\text{S}_{3/2} \rightarrow ^4\text{I}_{15/2}$ and $^4\text{F}_{9/2} \rightarrow ^4\text{I}_{15/2}$ transitions of Er^{3+} , respectively. Signal from the Si substrate could also be seen at ~ 550 nm as well as the signal from the pump at 532 nm. As observed from the parent bulks (**Figure 6d**), the green emission compared to the red one was the highest from the TeNa films and the lowest from the TeBi films when deposited using 30 W. A variation could be noted in the shape of the green emission band from the films compared to the corresponding targets suggesting that the Er^{3+} sites were probably impacted during the film deposition. No sharp peaks except those related to the Si substrate can be seen in the emission spectra, suggesting that the Er^{3+} are located in amorphous sites in the films. One should point out the absence of correlation between the ratio of the green to red emissions and the sputtering power.

Figure 6: Normalized emission spectra of the TeBa (a), TeBi (b) and TeNa (c) films deposited using various sputtering power on Si substrate ($\lambda_{exc} = 532$ nm). Insets show the red emission. Shown in (d) is the emission spectra of the parent bulk glasses ($\lambda_{exc} = 532$ nm). The spectra are normalized to the band at 660 nm.

The emission spectra normalized at 1612 nm which helped to take into account the reabsorption of Er^{3+} are presented in **Figure 7**. They showed an emission centered at ~ 1530 nm which could be related to the ${}^4I_{13/2} \rightarrow {}^4I_{15/2}$ transitions of Er^{3+} . The emission band was also broad without the appearance of sharp peaks confirming the location of Er^{3+} in amorphous sites. No significant changes in the shape of the emission could be seen when changing the film composition nor the sputtering power, indicating that the sites of the Er^{3+} are similar in all the films. This was in agreement with Lemiere et al. who also reported similar Er^{3+} sites in the TeBa, TeBi and TeNa bulk glasses.⁸ However, the shape of the emission band of the films is different from that of the corresponding bulks (**Figure 7d**). This discrepancy should be related to the sample thickness. As the bulk samples are ~ 1 mm thick, reabsorption processes are expected to occur, modifying the shape of the emission band. Moreover, compared to bulk, the films are closer to the nanoscale regime and with the ions being uniformly spaced in the glass film matrix, a single broad emission was noticed. A similar type of emission band was observed by Gsken et al. for a plasmonic waveguide containing Er^{3+} implanted on a 25 nm sputtered SiO_2 film.⁵⁰

Figure 7: Normalized emission spectra of the TeBa (a), TeBi (b) and TeNa (c) films deposited using various sputtering power on Si substrate ($\lambda_{exc} = 808$ nm). Shown in (d) is the emission spectra of the parent bulk glasses ($\lambda_{exc} = 808$ nm).

Several factors contribute to the surface roughness of the films. For example, temperature and pressure tend to influence the growth kinetics based on the type of deposition process being used. A study performed by Amirzada et al. demonstrated the difference in film surface roughness depending on the deposition process, highlighting the importance of growth kinetics and the environmental factors present during deposition while also providing insight on the influence of the type of substrate being used.⁵¹ The type and surface roughness of the substrate

is a major factor in the case of epitaxial film growth where the film critical thickness is in the order of atomic monolayers and the overall film thickness is less than tens of nanometers.^{52, 53} However, in this work the substrate should not have influence since the material of interest is not crystalline nor an alloy and the film thickness is in the range of hundreds of nanometers. Here, the surfaces of the as-deposited films were scanned with AFM and with an optical profiler so the film quality could be estimated from smaller and larger scale surfaces. The surface topography of the 30 W films measured with profilometer and AFM is presented in **Figure 8a, b and c** and in **Figure 8d, e and f** respectively.

Figure 8: Surface profiles of the as-deposited TeBa, TeBi and TeNa films deposited using 30W, measured using the optical profiler (a, b and c) and AFM (d, e and f) respectively.

As shown in **Figures 8a-c**, the surface of the as-deposited films is uniform without voids adding evidence about the absence of significant crystallization occurring during film deposition. Using AFM, 5×5 sq.μm areas were scanned and low RMS was obtained for the as-deposited TeBi and TeNa films whereas higher RMS was detected for the as-deposited TeBa films (**Table 4**). On using an optical profiler, larger RMS was measured on scanning a larger area. Nonetheless, the newly deposited films had similar RMS than films deposited for photovoltaic

technology⁵⁴ confirming the feasibility of depositing the new developed tellurite glasses into films with high surface quality using RF magnetron sputtering.

Table 4: RMS of the investigated films measured using AFM (scanning size of $5 \times 5 \text{ sq.}\mu\text{m}$) and optical profiler (scanning size depending on the sample)

Sputtering power (W)	RMS from AFM (nm) ($\pm 0.1 \text{ nm}$)		RMS from optical profiler (nm) ($\pm 10\%$)		
	as-deposited	after 8 months	scanned area	as-deposited	after 8 months
TeBa films					
30	1.25	2.5	27 mm \times 25 mm	190	220
40	0.3	1.5	30 mm \times 28 mm	250	335
50	0.4	1.2	27 mm \times 26 mm	180	225
TeBi films					
20	0.1	0.1	29 mm \times 25 mm	240	345
30	0.1	0.1	41 mm \times 31 mm	300	510
TeNa films					
20	0.1	1.5	34 mm \times 27 mm	360	550
30	0.4	1.6	36 mm \times 23 mm	525	

Also shown in **Figure 9** are the surfaces of the same films measured 8 months after deposition.

Figure 9: Surface profiles of the TeBa, TeBi and TeNa deposited using 30W, measured using the optical profiler (a-c) and AFM (d-f), respectively. They were measured 8 months after the deposition.

As shown in **Table 4**, the roughness of the TeBa and TeNa films (from both AFM and optical profiler) increased significantly overtime whereas no significant changes in surface roughness were observed for the TeBi films suggesting that these TeBi films were less sensitive to physical aging. A complete study of the (bulks and films) aging process is in progress to understand how to control the aging phenomena and so to improve the stability of the films overtime.

Conclusion

The present work demonstrates that the RF magnetron sputtering technique is a promising approach to deposit Er^{3+} doped tellurite films of complex composition. For the first time to the best of our knowledge, films with the composition $68.25 \text{ TeO}_2 - 19.5 \text{ ZnO} - 9.75 \text{ X} - 2.5 \text{ Er}_2\text{O}_3$ (in mol%), where $\text{X} = \text{BaO}, \text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3, \text{Na}_2\text{O}$ were successfully deposited with low surface roughness. In comparison with bulk glass targets, a small decrease in Te content was observed in the films leading to films with lower RI than the targets. The films prepared from the Bi_2O_3 containing glass target have the highest RI. Nonetheless, amorphous and transparent films were obtained with Er^{3+} emissions in the visible and NIR under excitation at 532 and 808 nm, respectively. The glass structure of the films was found to depend on the deposition parameters. An increase in sputtering power leads to films with more depolymerized network. The thin films containing Bi_2O_3 are found to be the most stable ones over time demonstrating that they are the most promising for integrated photonics and optical switches.

Acknowledgement

The work leading to this publication has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101092723/IBAIA. UK participants in Horizon Europe Project IBAIA are supported by UKRI grant number 10062902 (MODUS). The authors would also like to acknowledge the Academy of Finland

(Flagship Programme, Photonics Research, and Innovation PREIN No 320165 and 346518).

Authors also appreciate the financial support from grant LM2023037 from the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic. Dr. Rakesh Dhama, from Tampere University (Finland) is also acknowledged for fruitful discussion.

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